

Randomized Prospective Study to Compare Two Different Doses of Cisatracurium using Train of Four Neuro-Muscular Monitoring Regarding Intubating Conditions and Hemodynamic Parameters

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Abstract:

Background: Cisatracurium, a non-depolarizing neuromuscular blocking agent, is commonly used during general anaesthesia to facilitate tracheal intubation. However, determining the optimal dosing regimen to achieve favorable intubation conditions with minimal hemodynamic disturbances is essential for safer anaesthesia practice. Neuromuscular function monitoring through Train of Four (TOF) provides a reliable way to assess the depth of blockade and ensure smooth intubation.

Aims and Objectives: The primary objective of this study was to compare the effects of two different doses of cisatracurium (0.15 mg/kg and 0.20 mg/kg) on intubating conditions, including jaw relaxation, vocal cord mobility, and ease of laryngoscopy, along with the hemodynamic parameters such as blood pressure, heart rate, and oxygen saturation, using TOF neuromuscular monitoring.

Materials and Methods: This was a prospective, randomized, double-blinded clinical study conducted at the Department of Anaesthesiology, LLRM Medical College & SVBP Hospital, Meerut, India, over 18 months. A total of 80 patients, aged 18 to 65 years, classified as ASA I and II, were randomly divided into two groups of 40 patients each. Group A received 0.15 mg/kg of cisatracurium, while Group B received 0.20 mg/kg. TOF monitoring was used to assess neuromuscular blockade at intervals after drug administration, and intubation conditions were scored based on jaw relaxation, vocal cord mobility, and laryngoscopy ease. Hemodynamic parameters were recorded pre- and post-intubation.

Results: Patients in Group B (0.20 mg/kg) had significantly better intubating conditions, with 90% exhibiting easy jaw relaxation compared to 65% in Group A. Vocal cord mobility was better in Group B, with 90% of patients showing open vocal cords, compared to 68% in Group A. Laryngoscopy was easier in Group B (90% easy cases vs. 73% in Group A). Hemodynamic parameters such as systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, and oxygen saturation showed no significant differences between the groups. Group B had a significantly shorter onset time of blockade (154.4 seconds vs. 180.63 seconds) and a longer duration of blockade (41.58 minutes vs. 27.75 minutes).

Conclusion: Increasing the dose of cisatracurium from 0.15 mg/kg to 0.20 mg/kg improves intubation conditions without significant adverse hemodynamic effects. The higher dose provides faster onset and prolonged neuromuscular blockade, making it a more effective choice for achieving optimal intubation conditions.

Keywords: Cisatracurium, Intubating Conditions, Neuromuscular Blockade, Train of Four (TOF), Hemodynamic Parameters, Randomized Prospective Study.

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Introduction

Neuromuscular blocking agents (NMBAs) are integral to modern anaesthesia practice, facilitating endotracheal intubation and optimizing surgical

conditions by providing skeletal muscle relaxation. [1,2] Cisatracurium, a benzylisoquinolinium non-depolarizing NMBA, is widely favored due to its

intermediate duration of action, minimal histamine release, and organ-independent Hofmann elimination. [3] These characteristics suit patients with compromised renal or hepatic function. Despite its routine use, it remains critical to determine the optimal dosing regimen to balance effective intubating conditions with minimal adverse hemodynamic effects. [4]

Intubating conditions depend on achieving sufficient neuromuscular blockade, which can be assessed using Train of Four (TOF) neuromuscular monitoring. TOF allows for real-time neuromuscular function evaluation and NMBA dosage titration to achieve optimal blockade. However, varying doses of cisatracurium can lead to differences in intubating conditions and associated hemodynamic responses, such as changes in blood pressure and heart rate. [5, 6]

This randomized prospective study aims to compare two doses of cisatracurium using TOF monitoring to evaluate the quality of intubating conditions and hemodynamic parameters. The findings will provide insights into the optimal dosing of cisatracurium that ensures adequate intubation while minimizing potential hemodynamic disturbances, ultimately contributing to safer anaesthesia practice.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology at LLRM Medical College and SVBP Hospital, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India. The study involved patients undergoing elective surgeries under general anaesthesia, allowing for a controlled assessment of intubating and hemodynamic parameters under standardized conditions.

The study was carried out over 18 months, from October 2022 to April 2024, enabling the collection of sufficient data to evaluate the outcomes of two different doses of cisatracurium.

Study Design: This was a prospective, randomized, double-blinded study. The double-blinded nature ensured that both the anesthesiologists performing the intubation and the patients were unaware of the group assignments, thereby eliminating bias in assessing intubating conditions and hemodynamic responses.

Study Population: The Institutional Ethics Committee approved the study, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. A total of 80 patients were enrolled, all classified as American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II. The patients were between 18 and 65 years of age and of any gender. These patients were admitted for elective surgeries at SVBP Hospital associated with LLRM Medical College in Meerut. They were randomly assigned to one of two

groups, with 40 patients in each Group, using a computer-generated table for randomization.

Group Allocation: The 80 patients were randomly divided into two groups of 40 patients each. Group A received a loading dose of 0.15 mg/kg cisatracurium, while Group B received a loading dose of 0.20 mg/kg cisatracurium. Neuromuscular monitoring using Train of Four (TOF) was initiated after administering the loading dose and continued every 30 seconds for 4 minutes, followed by monitoring every 5 minutes up to 30 minutes.

Patients were eligible for inclusion if they were classified as ASA grade I or II, aged between 18 and 65, of either sex and scheduled for elective surgery under general anaesthesia. Patients were excluded if they refused participation, were pregnant or lactating, had a known sensitivity to neuromuscular blocking agents, had an anticipated difficult airway, or had a history of neurological, psychiatric, or respiratory diseases. Additionally, patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, severe systemic and cardiovascular disease (ASA III & IV), or obesity were excluded from the study.

The primary tool for neuromuscular monitoring was the TOF device, which is routinely used to assess the degree of neuromuscular blockade during anaesthesia induction. Other standard monitoring equipment included electrocardiogram (ECG), non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP) monitor, and pulse oximeter to track hemodynamic parameters such as heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation throughout the procedure. The neuromuscular monitor used was the STIMPOD NMS450X. Additional equipment included two working Macintosh laryngoscopes with blade sizes 3 and 4, anatomical face masks of sizes 3 and 4, cuffed endotracheal tubes, Guedel airways, bougies, stylets, and suction apparatus.

The anesthetic protocol was standardized across all patients to minimize confounding factors. The drugs used included Inj. Glycopyrrolate, Inj. Midazolam, Inj. Fentanyl Citrate, Inj. Propofol and Inj. Cisatracurium Besylate.

Anaesthesia Technique: After a preoperative assessment, including the patient's medical history, past surgeries, medication use, allergies, and routine investigations, the patients were fasted for at least 8 hours. On the day of surgery premedication inj glycopyrrolate (0.01 mg/kg) and inj midazolam (0.05mg/kg) was administered. Pre-oxygenation was performed with 100% oxygen for 3 minutes, followed by administering Inj. Fentanyl (1 mcg/kg). Neuromuscular monitoring with TOF was initiated using the STIMPOD NMS450X, starting with a low current of 10–20 mA, which was increased until four vigorous twitches were observed. Once a supramaximal stimulus was con-

firmed, induction proceeded with Inj. Propofol (1 mg/kg), followed by the assigned loading dose of cisatracurium. TOF monitoring was performed every 30 seconds for up to 4 minutes.

Tracheal intubation was performed once the TOF ratio was 0/4, and the intubating conditions were assessed based on jaw relaxation, laryngoscopy ease, vocal cord mobility, and patient response. The TOF ratio was monitored every 5 minutes to determine the clinical duration of the loading dose. Anaesthesia was maintained with a mixture of 66.6% nitrous oxide, 33.3% oxygen, and 0.6–1% isoflurane using a closed circuit with controlled ventilation. Hemodynamic parameters were recorded at various time points from 1 minute to 30 minutes after administration of the neuromuscular blocking agent.

Data Collection: Data collected included demographic information, preoperative risk factors, intraoperative parameters, and postoperative outcomes. Intubating conditions were evaluated using a predefined scoring system based on ease of intubation, jaw relaxation, vocal cord mobility, and patient response. Hemodynamic parameters such as heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and oxygen saturation were recorded at specified intervals. Adverse events, such as coughing or limb movement, and complications were documented and analyzed.

Scoring Systems

- **Cormack-Lehane Grading:** Used to assess laryngoscopic view, with Grade 1 indicating complete visualization of the vocal cords and Grade 4 indicating no glottic structures visible.

- **Intubation Score:** Evaluated jaw relaxation, laryngoscopy ease, vocal cord mobility, coughing, and limb movement. Scores ranged from 5 (excellent) to 15 (poor).
- **Muzi Score:** Assessed jaw relaxation, scoring 1 (complete relaxation) to 3 (resistance, unable to open).

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, or ANOVA as appropriate. Results were interpreted to identify significant differences between the two dose groups regarding intubating conditions, TOF ratios, and hemodynamic stability. Adverse events and complications were documented and compared between groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

A total of 80 patients were enrolled in this study and were equally randomized into two groups, Group A and Group B, each consisting of 40 participants. The gender distribution in both groups showed no significant difference, with Group A having 42.5% males and 57.5% females, and Group B having 52.5% males and 47.5% females ($p > 0.05$). Additionally, no significant differences were found in age and weight between the groups. The mean age for both groups was 36.5 years ($p = 1.00$), while the mean weight was 54.8 kg for Group A and 56.83 kg for Group B ($p = 0.07$). Similarly, the distribution of ASA grades between the groups was not significantly different, with Group A having 50% ASA Grade I patients and Group B having 52.5% ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Parameter	Group A (Mean ± SD)	Group B (Mean ± SD)	p-Value
Age (years)	36.5 ± 12.21	36.5 ± 12.57	1.000
Weight (kg)	54.8 ± 4.91	56.83 ± 4.93	0.07
ASA Grade I (%)	50	52.5	> 0.05
ASA Grade II (%)	50	47.5	> 0.05

Jaw relaxation was significantly better in Group B (90% easy opening) compared to Group A (65% easy opening). In Group A, 35% of patients experienced mild resistance during jaw opening, while only 10% of patients in Group B had this issue ($p = 0.0069$). No patient in either Group experienced rigid jaw opening (Table 2).

Table 2: Jaw Relaxation

Jaw Relaxation	Group A (n = 40)	Group B (n = 40)	p-Value
Easy Opening (%)	65	90	0.0069
Mild resistance (%)	35	10	-

Vocal cord mobility was significantly better in Group B, where 90% of patients had open vocal cords compared to 68% in Group A. In Group A, 32% of patients had moving vocal cords, while only 10% of Group B patients experienced this ($p = 0.037$). No patients in either Group had closed vocal cords (Table 3).

Table 3: Vocal Cord Mobility

Vocal Cord Mobility	Group A (n = 40)	Group B (n = 40)	p-Value
Open (%)	68	90	0.037
Moving (%)	32	10	-

Laryngoscopy was significantly easier in Group B, with 90% of patients having easy laryngoscopy compared to 73% in Group A. While 25% of Group A patients experienced slight resistance during laryngoscopy, this was reduced to 10% in Group B ($p = 0.013$). One patient in Group A experienced difficulty during laryngoscopy, while no such cases were noted in Group B. Coughing was more prevalent in Group A, where 33% of patients exhibited slight coughing during intubation, compared to only 10% in Group B. The number of patients with no coughing was significantly higher in Group B (90%) compared to Group A (68%) ($p = 0.013$). Limb movement was significantly reduced in Group B. While 40% of Group A patients experienced slight limb movement, only 7% of Group B patients had this issue. In Group A, 60% had no limb movement, compared to 93% in Group B ($p = 0.00047$).

The intubation score was significantly better in Group B, with 73% of patients having an excellent intubation score, compared to 28% in Group A. While 68% of Group A patients had a good score, only 28% in Group B had a good score ($p = 0.000027$). No patients in Group B had a poor intubation score, while 5% of Group A patients fell into this category.

There was no significant difference in systolic blood pressure between the two groups. The increase in SBP observed between 3 and 4 minutes after administering the neuromuscular blocking agent was attributed to the stress response from intubation. This returned to baseline levels by 7–8 minutes. The SBP values did not show statistical significance at any time points between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). Similar to SBP, the two groups had no significant differences in diastolic blood pressure ($p > 0.05$). Heart rate measurements showed no significant differences between the two groups at any time ($p > 0.05$). A transient increase in heart rate at 3–4 minutes post-intubation was observed, which returned to baseline by 7–8 minutes. No significant differences were noted in oxygen saturation between the two groups ($p > 0.05$).

Train of Four (TOF) Monitoring showed that the onset time of neuromuscular blockade was significantly shorter in Group B. The mean onset time in Group A was 180.63 ± 3.68 seconds, while in Group B, it was 154.40 ± 2.30 seconds ($p = 0.000$).

The duration of the neuromuscular blockade was significantly longer in Group B. Group A had a mean blockade duration of 27.75 ± 5.05 minutes, while Group B had a duration of 41.58 ± 3.46 minutes ($p = 0.000$) (table 4).

Table 4: Onset Time and Duration of Blockade

Parameter	Group A (Mean \pm SD)	Group B (Mean \pm SD)	p-Value
Onset Time (seconds)	180.63 ± 3.68	154.40 ± 2.30	0.000
Duration of Blockade (minutes)	27.75 ± 5.05	41.58 ± 3.46	0.000

Discussion

The role of muscle relaxants is crucial in ensuring the safety of anaesthesia and providing optimal operating conditions. Cisatracurium is considered an ideal muscle relaxant due to its rapid onset of action, absence of histamine release, and reduced production of laudanosine, a nephrotoxic metabolite. This study aimed to compare two doses of cisatracurium regarding intubating conditions and hemodynamic parameters. Specifically, the study evaluated the onset of action, intubation score, duration of action, and hemodynamic parameters of these doses.

Regarding intubating conditions, 28% of patients in Group A had excellent conditions, while 68% had good conditions. In Group B, 73% of patients experienced excellent intubating conditions, and 27% had good conditions. The comparison between the groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), aligning with the findings of El Kasaby et al [7], who reported better intubating conditions with higher doses. Blustein et al. [8] also recommended an intubating dose of 0.15mg/kg cisatracurium.

Regarding the duration of action of the neuromuscular blocking agent, the mean and standard deviation for the Group was 27.75 ± 5.05 minutes. Group B showed a more prolonged duration of 41.58 ± 3.46 minutes, with a statistically significant p-value of < 0.05 . These results are consistent with the studies by Blustein et al. [8] and El Kasaby et al [7].

The onset time for Group A had a mean and standard deviation of 180 ± 3.68 seconds, compared to 154.4 ± 2.30 seconds in Group B, indicating a faster onset of action in Group B. These findings are similar to the results of Melinghoff et al [9]. and Blustein et al [8]., demonstrating that a 4xED95 dose of cisatracurium has a faster onset than a 3xED95 dose, with statistical significance.

Changes in heart rate, systolic, and diastolic blood pressure at specified intervals post-loading dose were comparable between the two groups, showing no statistical significance. This aligns with the studies by Lien et al [10]. and Basta et al. [11]., who reported minimal changes in mean heart rate and blood pressure with cisatracurium and atracurium.

No decrease in blood pressure or increase in heart rate was observed.

Furthermore, there were no signs of flushing at the injection site, erythema, histamine release, or other adverse effects. Suresh SN et al [12]. emphasized the importance of monitoring neuromuscular blockade at the adductor pollicis over the orbicularis oculi. Woo Jong Shin et al. found that the onset of action and recovery was faster at the laryngeal adductors than at the adductor pollicis, indicating that although the adductor pollicis reflects upper airway muscle paralysis, it is not sufficient to determine a patient's readiness for intubation due to the earlier blockade of laryngeal muscles.

Conclusion

Higher doses of cisatracurium (4 X ED95), i.e., 0.20mg/kg, in comparison to lower doses (3 X ED95), i.e., 0.15mg/kg, provide an efficient and more rapid onset with a longer duration of action and comparable hemodynamic status without any clinical signs of histamine release. Clinical recovery from skeletal neuromuscular blockade was normal in both groups.

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